

MEDICAL SCIENCES

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COMPLICATIONS DURING PROSTHETICS WITH SOLID-CAST AND METAL-CERAMIC PROSTHESES

Abstract.

Periodontal complications (T84) in prosthetics with cast and metal-ceramic bridge prostheses include serous and hypertrophic gingivitis, gingival margin recession and periodontitis. These complications arise both from insufficient treatment of gingivitis or periodontitis before prosthetics and from unfavorable factors after it, such as deep immersion of the subgingival part of the crown and circulatory disorders. The main pathogenetic factor is the dysfunction of the periodontal supporting apparatus. The microvascular system of the periodontium and dental pulp acts as a pump, providing blood supply. Preparation of the supporting teeth negatively affects the periodontal vessels, causing an inflammatory reaction and multiple microcirculation disorders. During preparation of hard tissues, significant grinding (up to 1.5-2 mm) can occur, increasing inflammation. These factors are important for differential diagnosis, determining indications for preventive and therapeutic measures and ensuring professional liability in insurance medicine.

Key words: dental pulp, periodontal tissue, tooth, prosthesis, inflammatory reaction, insurance medicine

Based on literature data [1-8] on pathogenetic mechanisms, clinical manifestations of periodontitis (CR5) and the ICD-11-C classification, pathological conditions of the periodontium during prosthetics with solid-cast bridges and metal-ceramic prostheses can be designated by a general definition - periodontal complications (T84) [6]. In the conditions of insurance medicine, the requirements for the quality, efficiency and reliability (durability) of dentures, especially expensive ones (solid and metal-ceramic), have increased significantly. Therefore, much attention has recently been paid to periodontal complications (gingivitis, apical and marginal periodontitis) that occur during and after orthopedic treatment [1-8]. When using prosthetics with solid-cast bridges and metal-ceramic prostheses, periodontal complications of 4 main types most often occur: 1) serous gingivitis and 2) hypertrophic; 3) recession of the gingival margin of the supporting teeth; 4) periodontitis [1-8]. These complications are observed in 2 main variants: 1. In case of insufficiently cured gingivitis or periodontitis before prosthetics. 2. The development of these processes after prosthetics under the influence of a number of unfavorable factors: deep immersion of the subgingival part of the artificial crown of the bridge. 3. Impaired blood circulation and metabolism in periodontal tissues, in particular under the influence of risk factors [1-8]. The main pathogenetic factor causing the occurrence of periodontal complications is a violation of the functioning mechanism of the supporting apparatus of the periodontal tooth.

The main role in the function of chewing (biting) food belongs to the vessels of the periodontal membrane of the tooth and the processes regulating its function:

1. General vascular system of periodontal tissues and dental pulp.
2. Capillary sphincters.
3. Inflammatory hyperemia of the capillaries of the dental pulp.
4. Arterial and venous anastomoses of periodontal vessels and dental pulp.
5. Arteriovenous shunt of the vessels of the apical part of the periodontium and dental pulp.
6. Arteriovenous half-shunts.
7. Vascular pumps of the periodontal membrane.

The microvascular system of the periodontium - dental pulp, by its mechanism of action, resembles the operation of a pump or shock absorber, in which the vessels of the periodontium and dental pulp, by the mechanism of their action, perform the function of cylinders, and the bypass nozzle is the vessels of the apical foramen of the tooth root. When chewing or pressing on the tooth, blood is squeezed out of the vessels of the periodontal membrane and mainly passes into the vessels of the dental pulp, and during the subsequent chewing phase (pause - removal of chewing pressure), the movement of blood through the periodontal-tooth pulp microvascular system occurs in the opposite direction. This mechanism is a kind of local (tissue) blood transfusion pump, which, in addition to pulse fluctuations, provides highly effective blood supply (working hyperemia) to the supporting apparatus of the tooth when

chewing food, ensuring periodontal function in a broad aspect - trophism, oxygen regime, etc. Preparation of abutment teeth of bridge prostheses under artificial crowns has a negative effect on the tissues of abutment teeth, especially on periodontal vessels, mainly the periodontal membrane, which largely determine its trophism, metabolism and support function, since the microvasculature of the periodontal membrane provides hydraulic shock-absorbing (hydrodempting) mechanisms of the supporting functions of the tooth. These processes are most pronounced under conditions of increased chewing load, which affects the periodontium of supporting teeth when using bridges, which appears during the preparation of hard dental tissues. When preparing abutment teeth of bridges for artificial stamped crowns, an inflammatory reaction occurs in the periodontal tissues, which occurs with a sharp disruption of microcirculation (short-term hyperemia is replaced by long-term venous stagnation). When preparing abutment teeth for solid-cast and metal-ceramic bridges, significant grinding of hard tissues occurs (up to 1.5-2 mm) and the inflammatory reaction in periodontal tissues (especially in the vessels of the periodontal membrane) sharply increases [2, 3, 7, 8]. These data are essential when performing the following manipulations:

1. Differential diagnosis of the above disorders and diseases.
2. Determination of indications for carrying out adequate preventive and therapeutic measures.
3. Prevention and treatment of diseases taking into account the requirements of professional responsibility and professional risks, which is especially important in the conditions of insurance medicine and compulsory medical insurance with increased patient requirements for the quality, efficiency and reliability of prevention and treatment.
4. Use, as indicated, of high-tech equipment and methods that meet the requirements of the national project "Health" [9].

The effectiveness and long-term functioning of solid-cast bridges and metal-ceramic dentures mainly depends on a number of mandatory conditions:

1. Qualitatively cured abutment teeth after pulpitis, periodontitis and periodontitis.
2. Prevention of recession of the gingival margin and exposure of the necks of supporting teeth, especially in the manufacture of metal-ceramic dentures.
3. The presence of overload or underload of the supporting teeth before prosthetics.
4. Rational design of the bridge, taking into account the optimal ratio of the number of supporting teeth and the area of the intermediate part of the prosthesis.
5. Exclusion as supporting teeth in the formation of ankylosis of the apical part of the tooth root [1-8].

In pursuance of the order of the Ministry of Health and Social Development of the Russian Federation No. 488 of June 20, 2007 on the rules for issuing permits for new medical technologies, the text of the article provides links to the main permitting documents for the use of magnetic laser and high-intensity laser radiation, devices and preventive and therapeutic techniques approved by the Ministry of Health and Social Development of the Russian Federation (permit formats documents have been repeatedly changed over time, so they are presented in chronological order and form. In clinical practice, very often, many doctors unjustifiably depulpate intact abutment teeth without proper justification for this. Usually,

over time, these depulped teeth demineralize, become brittle and lose the necessary strength for support. metal-ceramic prostheses. According to a number of authors, when preparing abutment teeth with preserved pulp, complications amount to up to 9.5%. Preservation of the pulp of abutment teeth during prosthetics with metal-ceramic bridges is justified, especially with the use of precautionary methods [1]. In the control group (comparison group), 286 patients were examined and treated using traditional methods (including archival data from co-developing institutions). Patients from the comparison group, after preparation and impression taking, felt sharp pain in the gingival margin around the supporting teeth. The pain often intensified when eating food, especially hard, salty, sour, etc., which forced these patients to seek help from their doctor. Inflammatory phenomena persisted for up to 8-10 days, and in patients with initial manifestations of periodontal disease - even longer. This is primarily due to the depth of preparation of hard tooth tissues, retraction of the gingival margin and the creation of a subgingival ledge. Odontopreparation of the crowns of abutment teeth for bridge-like metal-ceramic prostheses is carried out with the application of a solution of "Glumadesensitizer", calcicur and other new, mainly fluoride-containing preparations to protect the pulp of the prepared abutment teeth. Odontopreparation of the crowns of supporting teeth is also carried out in a gentle way under local anesthesia, often injection, for example, a 2% solution of lidocaine and other anesthetics. To reduce inflammation during gum retraction, anti-inflammatory components are used. Non-retraction techniques were also used, which significantly reduced damage to the gingival margin. The dental semiconductor diode device "Optodan" [10, 12] was chosen for the prevention and treatment of periodontal complications as it has a wide range of preventive and therapeutic effects (Fig. 8), and specifically on pathogenetic factors, primarily on the vessels of the periodontal membrane of supporting teeth, anti-inflammatory actions, etc. The device is used in several modifications: exposure to magnetic laser radiation directly on the foci of pathology on channel I (3-5 procedures), and then on channel II - 3-4 procedures. In the second option, in case of severe pathology, local irradiation is combined with the effect of magnetic laser radiation on the glomus-paragingliary regulatory system (Fig. 9), which has a pronounced general pathogenetic effect on the main pathogenetic mechanisms of the pathological process in the periodontium. The manifestation of hypertrophic gingivitis can also be successfully eliminated using a high-intensity laser device such as a computer-controlled laser scalpel "Lancet" (see Fig. 7), which also has a wide range of preventive and therapeutic effects in the high energy range of about 60 W (Fig. 10). With the help of this device, hypertrophic gingivitis is treated in a gentle way in two ways. The first is cutting off the hypertrophic tissue of the marginal gum with preliminary cooling of this area of tissue with chlorethyl: in this case, the high energy of the laser beam is used to reduce the temperature of the tissue and the cells suffer less from the effects of the high temperature of the laser beam. In the 2nd option, another method is used - this

is the denaturation of cells by exposure to low - up to 80-100 ° C - temperature at a power of 0.5-1 W, exposure time of 0.5-0.8 minutes. In this variant, the cells are not destroyed at all (by the type of ablation), do not stop their vital activity and are rejected from the underlying tissue in the form of a colliculative scab (see Fig. 10). It is important that under the formed scab there is increased epithelization of the surface of the mucous membrane of the gums and its rapid healing. In 846 patients who received magnetic laser radiation, the clinical picture in the area of prepared abutment teeth was more favorable compared to the comparison group. Firstly, there was no inflammation and swelling of the gingival margin, deepening of the periodontal groove, formation of periodontal pockets, etc. X-ray control revealed a picture of stabilization of the pathological process in the periodontal tissues of the supporting teeth. Patients who were previously exposed to magnetic laser radiation on their abutment teeth before preparation did not complain of sharp painful sensations (discomfort). In patients whose teeth were covered with plastic crowns during prosthetics, the above complications were not observed. When teeth are irradiated by magnetic lasers immediately after their preparation, no pronounced inflammatory reactions occur in periodontal tissues. In patients whose supporting teeth were exposed to magnetic laser radiation, the phenomena noted in the comparison group were not observed (see above). To fulfill the above conditions, a new method of intensive corrective action on the main pathogenetic link of the supporting apparatus of abutment teeth was developed: on the microvascular system periodontium-tooth pulp, which, due to the hydrodamping effect, ensures the chewing function of the supporting apparatus of the tooth, namely the periodontal membrane. To stimulate the supporting apparatus of the tooth, based on the model of its functions outlined above, the microcirculation of the periodontal membrane was exposed to magnetic laser radiation using the Optodan dental apparatus. This device also provides a wide range of preventive and therapeutic effects: relief of inflammation and swelling, stimulation of tissue metabolism, regeneration, etc. This method was used on a representative clinical sample (846 patients) with a fairly high treatment efficiency in most patients (more than 89%).

CONCLUSION The conducted representative studies allow us to draw a conclusion about the pronounced effectiveness of the use of magnetic laser radiation for the prevention of periodontal complications during prosthetics with solid-cast bridges and metal-ceramic prostheses and to recommend this method for improving the quality, efficiency and reliability of orthopedic treatment in the conditions of insurance medicine and compulsory medical insurance at the level of the requirements of the national project "Health" [9]. System analysis [9] showed that, based on literature data and our own, mechanisms and systems for regulating the supporting apparatus of abutment teeth of bridge-like solid cast and metal-ceramic prostheses, namely the microcirculation system of the periodontal membrane, were determined [1-8]. The leading role of the vessels of the periodontal membrane in the pathogenesis and

methods of rehabilitation of impaired functions of the supporting apparatus of the tooth has been revealed [8]. A significant role was played by special studies using functional methods (rheo- and photoplethysmography, laser and ultrasound flowmetry, automated computer-laser systems "Endodontics" and "Diast" [9]), which made it possible to identify the leading pathogenetic factors of diseases in various groups of patients depending on the form, nature, severity and other features and, accordingly, determine the features of preventive and therapeutic methods of influence depending on the identified features. It is important to emphasize that using fairly representative clinical material (846 patients), it was possible to establish positive results and favorable treatment outcomes in 89% of patients with a sufficient degree of probability (efficiency, reliability).

References.

1. M.L. Mironova – «S#emnye protezy», 2009, «GJeOTAR-Media», Moskva – str.89
2. I.Ju. Lebedenko, Je.S. Kalivradzhijan, T.I. Ibragimov – «Rukovodstvo po ortopedicheskoj stomatologii», 2005, Medicinskoe informacionnoe agentstvo, Moskva – str.231
3. V.N. Kopejkin, M.Z. Mirgazitov – «Ortopedicheskaja stomatologija», 2001, «Medicina», Moskva – str.260
4. Gazhva S.I., Pashinjan G.A., Aleshina O.A. – «Analiz oshibok i oslozhnenij pri protezirovanii s primeneniem nes#emnyh ortopedicheskikh konstrukcij».
5. Iordanishvili A.K., Tolmachev I.A., Muzykin M.I., Panchuk Ju.P., Golovko A.A. – «Professional'nyj oshibki i defekty okazaniya medicinskoj pomoshhi pri stomatologicheskoj rehabilitacii vzroslyh pacientov».
6. Gazhva S.I., Aleshina O.A. – «Zhaloby pacientov kak odin iz pokazatelej kachestva raboty stomatologa-ortopeda».
7. Mihal'chenko D.V., Gumilevskij B.Ju., Naumova V.N., Virabjan V.A., Zhidovinov A.V., Golovchenko S.G. – «Dinamika immunologicheskikh pokazatelej v processe adaptacii k nes#emnym ortopedicheskim konstrukcijam».
8. Iordanishvili A.K., Tolmachev I.A., Bobunov D.N., Gorbatenkov M.E., Sagalatyj A.M. – «Defekty i oslozhnenija pri protezirovanii nes#emnymi zubnymi protezami».
9. Motorkina T.V., Poljanskaja O.G., Shemonaev V.I. – «Vozmozhnye oslozhnenija na jetapah pol'zovanija cel'nolitymi metallokeramicheskimi konstrukcijami».
10. Romodanovskij P.O., Urukov Ju.N. – «Otkaz ot pol'zovanija s#emnymi zubnymi protezami kak odin iz faktorov razvitija konfliktnyh situacij».
11. Zholudev S.E. – «Analiz oshibok i oslozhnenij, dopushhennyh pri izgotovlenii s#emnyh konstrukcij zubnyh protezov, po dannym konsul'tativnogo professorskogo priema».
12. Seferjan K., Seferjan N.Ju., Lapina N.V. – «Disfunkcional'nye narusheniya v visochno-nizhecheljustnyh sustavah kak rezul'tat oshibok protezirovanija s#emnymi ortopedicheskimi konstrukcijami».